

SIMULATION OF REVERSE WOOD BIOMASS SUPPLY CHAINS FOR EMISSION-EFFICIENT LOGISTICS SCENARIOS

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Abstract

The increasing importance of renewable energy highlights the need for efficient logistics in Reversed supply Chains of Wood Biomass (RSCWB). This study evaluates the cost and emission effectiveness of alternative organisational scenarios for wood biomass logistics in Poland. A simulation model was developed using historical industry data, forest resource statistics, and actual transport price lists, incorporating cost structures, vehicle parameters, and carbon footprint factors. Four potential processing locations were analysed through a scenario based approach supported by GIS based distance matrices. Results indicate significant regional variability in both costs and emissions, with Biała Rawska emerging as the most cost-effective option (931 million PLN; 57.7 million kgCO_{2e}), while Czekanka showed the highest costs (over 1 billion PLN) with only limited emission benefits. The findings underline the crucial role of location selection and transport organisation in improving the efficiency and sustainability of RSCWB. The study contributes a practical methodological framework for assessing reverse biomass flows, offering insights for both policymakers and industry stakeholders in advancing circular economy strategies.

Keywords: reverse logistics, efficiency simulation, wood biomass, efficiency

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for renewable energy sources has positioned biomass, and particularly wood biomass, as a central component of sustainable energy systems (Nunes et al., 2020). Wood residues, waste wood, and by-products from forestry and wood processing industries constitute valuable resources that can be mobilized through efficient supply chains (Demirbas, 2004). Traditional biomass supply chains are usually linear extending from raw material extraction to energy conversion (Nunes et al., 2020). However research by (Kawa, 2023) underline an increasing importance of the role of Reversed Supply Chains of Wood Biomass (RSCWB). These complex supply chain concepts account for the return, recovery, and redistribution of biomass resources, including post consumer wood and industrial by-products, which enhances both resource efficiency and environmental performance (Dubisz et al., 2024; Hrechyn et al., 2021). Therefore, an in depth research on its process efficiency improvement is essential.

The effectiveness of RSCWB is contingent on multiple interacting factors: collection logistics, storage, transportation, processing capacity, and market demand. Effectiveness may be assessed not only from economical, but also ecological and social perspective (Hrechyn et al., 2021). This empowers the introduction of Circular Economy elements within supply chains to enhance the sustainable character of those (Werner-Lewandowska et al., 2024). However it has to be concerned that regional and temporal variability in biomass availability adds to the complexity of designing optimal organisational setups (Kawa et al., 2025). Given this complexity, it is essential not only to conceptualise reversed supply chains but also to evaluate their effectiveness under diverse operational and organisational conditions (Dubisz, 2023). A scenario-based approach emerges as a powerful tool in this context, allowing decision-makers to test and compare alternative supply chain configurations of transport processes. Introduction of Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis support the identification of trade-offs, and mitigate risks (Zajac et al., 2024).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on biomass supply chains has expanded significantly over the last two decades, with a growing emphasis on efficiency, resilience, and sustainability (Calvano et al., 2025). Early works primarily focused on forward logistics, addressing the cost and energy balance of transporting bulky and low-density biomass (Ekşioğlu et al., 2009; Rentizelas et al., 2009). However, more recent studies incorporate reverse logistics, recognising that wood residues and waste streams represent substantial untapped resources (Ackom et al., 2013; Babuka et al., 2020; Dubisz et al., 2023). Reverse supply chains enable circularity by redirecting post-consumer and industrial wood towards bioenergy or material recycling, thereby reducing dependence on virgin resources and lowering greenhouse gas emissions (Sulaiman et al., 2020). Studies on the effectiveness of reversed biomass supply chains often evaluate performance in terms of logistics costs, energy efficiency, and environmental impacts. Modelling approaches such as mixed-integer linear programming, multi-objective optimisation,

and life cycle assessment (LCA) are commonly applied to assess trade-offs between cost and sustainability (Kumar et al., 2023). Despite these methodological advances, challenges persist in capturing uncertainty in feedstock supply, market demand, and regulatory frameworks. To address this uncertainty, scenario-based analysis has been widely recommended. Scenario approaches allow researchers to simulate different organisational setups, collection schemes, and policy interventions, testing their influence on overall supply chain effectiveness including cascading utilization (Geldermann et al., 2016). For instance, scenarios can compare decentralised versus centralised collection systems, short versus long transport distances, or the integration of reverse flows with existing forward supply chains (Krstić et al., 2022). This approach helps also to identify robust strategies focused on transport emissions mitigation under varying future conditions, making it a particularly valuable decision-support tool in biomass logistics research. Research in chemistry industry logistic companies conducted by et al., (2019) revealed that tools like CO₂ calculators and IT support can help supply chains measure and manage emissions. Promoting multimodal transport reduces road dependence and lowers CO₂. Those elements could be incorporated within RSCWB to improve those digitalisation level and provide beneficial influence for management processes.

In summary, the literature demonstrates that reversed supply chains for wood biomass have significant potential to improve resource efficiency and sustainability. However, their effectiveness depends on well-designed organisational structures, logistics coordination, and market integration. The scenario approach stands out as a methodological necessity, enabling systematic evaluation of alternative supply chain setups and supporting stakeholders in making informed, long-term decisions.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology combines a literature review with a scenario-based simulation of reversed wood biomass supply chains in Poland. Building on existing studies, a simulation model has been developed to evaluate trade-offs between cost and carbon emissions under alternative organisational setups. Historical data from a wood biomass processing company are used alongside official forestry statistics to estimate regional biomass availability. Transport scenarios are constructed by integrating GIS-based distance matrices, real carrier price lists, and vehicle emission factors. Four potential processing centre locations are tested, enabling comparative analysis of logistics efficiency. This approach provides a practical framework for assessing how reverse logistics can balance economic and environmental objectives, while also identifying the spatial and organisational conditions that influence these trade-offs.

Research gap has been formulated, and it's based on the observation that existing studies rarely employ simulation-based approaches to comprehensively analyze the trade-offs between transportation costs and carbon emissions. Existing research rarely integrates simulation-based approaches to systematically evaluate the trade-offs between transportation costs and carbon emissions in reversed wood biomass logistics networks. Most current studies either focus exclusively on cost minimization or

emission reduction, or they assess both aspects in isolation without exploring their interdependencies and dynamic trade-offs. Furthermore, the potential of reverse logistics simulation as a decision-support tool for identifying, visualizing, and optimizing these trade-offs remains not sufficiently examined. Drawing on the literature analysis conducted and in relation to the requirement to verify the practical aspects of organizing RSCWB, the following research questions were formulated.

Research Question 1: How can reverse logistics simulation help identify trade-offs between cost and emissions in reversed supply chains of wood biomass?

Research Question 2: What are the key trade-offs between transport costs and carbon emissions in reversed supply chains of wood biomass?

The novelty of this research lies in the integration of simulation methods with real operational data, enabling the assessment of reversed wood biomass supply chains not only in theoretical terms but also in practical application. Unlike earlier studies that modelled generic biomass logistics, this work employs actual transport price structures, emission factors, and region-specific forest resource data to construct a decision support framework grounded in market realities. It extends existing models by linking cost and environmental performance to specific organisational scenarios, providing actionable insights for both industry practitioners and policymakers. This operationalised approach represents methodological advancement, as it demonstrates how RSCWB can be evaluated under real economic and regulatory conditions, thereby strengthening their role in circular economy strategies. In the **Figure 2** a general research methodology has been presented.

Figure 2 Research methodology

Source: own elaboration

4. SIMULATION ASSUMPTION

The simulation was conducted using historical data from the wood biomass processing company located in Poland. Hence actual wood biomass volume estimations reflect the actual trends in wood biomass flows. Actual carriers price lists were used to compare cost parameters, presenting cost values and their structure. The proposed locations result from the distribution of wood biomass processing centers in individual voivodeships in Poland. Applying these, an estimation of the most effective logistics organizational scenario was performed. The simulations carried out to determine the optimal variant of wood biomass transport organisation were based on the size of forested areas in Poland. Forests are a key source of timber for further processing and wood biomass conversion. Since the data revealing only an area (ha) was not sufficient, it was necessary to translate it into an approximate forest volume (m³). Considering the specific characteristics of Polish forests, a conversion factor of 280 m³/ha was applied (Statistics Poland, 2024). To ensure accurate transformation, the following calculation **Equation 1** was employed.

Equation 1 Formula for the conversion of forest area into its volume

$$\text{Standing volume (m}^3\text{)} = \text{Forest area (ha)} \times \text{Average growing stock (m}^3\text{/ha)}$$

Source: own elaboration based on UNECE & FAO, (2010).

The **Table 7** below presents statistical data on the area of forests in voivodeships and their volume after conversion. According to (Statistics Poland, 2024) it allows for estimating the necessary means of transport capacity and conducting further simulations regarding the efficiency of their usage.

Table 7 The size of forests in Poland and the conversion of forest area into volume

Voivodeship	Forest area (ha)	Estimated standing volume (m ³)	Forest harvest (m ³)	Index of deforestation to its area
Dolnośląskie	630 000	176 400 000	108 519	0.062%
Kujawsko-Pomorskie	410 000	114 800 000	66 175	0.058%
Lubelskie	570 000	159 600 000	85 574	0.054%
Lubuskie	690 000	193 200 000	109 091	0.056%
Łódzkie	380 000	106 400 000	60 869	0.057%
Małopolskie	470 000	131 600 000	86 358	0.066%
Mazowieckie	910 000	254 800 000	141 494	0.056%
Opolskie	250 000	70 000 000	39 192	0.056%
Podkarpackie	680 000	190 400 000	117 515	0.062%
Podlaskie	620 000	173 600 000	111 785	0.064%
Pomorskie	665 000	186 200 000	102 953	0.055%
Śląskie	365 000	102 200 000	61 602	0.060%
Świętokrzyskie	370 000	103 600 000	66 877	0.065%
Warmińsko-Mazurskie	830 000	232 400 000	147 869	0.064%
Wielkopolskie	770 000	215 600 000	143 884	0.067%
Zachodniopomorskie	820 000	229 600 000	134 128	0.058%

Source: own elaboration based on Forest Statistical Yearbook (2024)

Forest density was presented in **Figure 3** below to visualize the potential and localization of wood biomass harvesting sources in Poland. With regard to the indicated forest density in Poland, four locations for wood biomass processing centers were proposed:

- Runowo, post code: 62-035
- Biała Rawska, post code: 96-230
- Kwidzyń, post code: 82-500
- Czekanka, post code: 42-470

The selection of the most cost-effective location and the assessment of transport emissions were conducted in the further part of this research.

Figure 3 Total forest area(ha) in Poland in 2024

Source: own elaboration based on Forest Statistical Yearbook (2024)

In the next step, the ratio of the amount of wood biomass harvested to the area and volume of forests was determined. The information is presented in **Table 8**. On this basis, the wood biomass production potential coefficient was determined, depending on the volume of forests.

Table 8 Wood biomass harvesting potential in relation to forest volume

Voivodeship	Forest area (ha)	Estimated standing volume (m3)	Total biomass (m3)	Wood biomass ratio to forest standing volume
Dolnośląskie	7 560 000	176 400 000	2 528 496	0.0123
Kujawsko-Pomorskie	4 920 000	114 800 000	1 645 663	0.0125
Lubelskie	6 840 000	159 600 000	2 294 587	0.0126
Lubuskie	8 280 000	193 200 000	2 751 477	0.0125
Łódzkie	4 560 000	106 400 000	1 494 611	0.0123
Małopolskie	5 640 000	131 600 000	1 870 940	0.0124
Mazowieckie	10 920 000	254 800 000	3 791 222	0.0130
Opolskie	3 000 000	70 000 000	1 026 855	0.0128
Podkarpackie	8 160 000	190 400 000	2 702 901	0.0124
Podlaskie	7 440 000	173 600 000	2 492 004	0.0126
Pomorskie	7 980 000	186 200 000	2 660 134	0.0125
Śląskie	4 380 000	102 200 000	1 462 919	0.0125
Świętokrzyskie	4 440 000	103 600 000	1 546 819	0.0134
Warmińsko-Mazurskie	9 960 000	232 400 000	3 397 107	0.0128

Wielkopolskie	9 240 000	215 600 000	3 131 121	0.0127
Zachodniopomorskie	9 840 000	229 600 000	3 241 523	0.0124
Total / average	113 160 000	2 640 400 000	38 038 380	0.0126

Source: own elaboration based on Forest Statistical Yearbook (2024)

The overview of biomass quantities broken down by voivodeship indicates the dominant role of the Mazowieckie, Warmińsko-Mazurskie, Wielkopolskie and Zachodniopomorskie voivodeships. Simultaneously, it has to be noticed that there is a stable relationship between biomass quantities and forest standing volume in each voivodeship. Subsequently, the ratio of forest size by voivodeship to the amount of wood biomass harvested was visualized. The calculated ratio is presented in **Figure 4** below.

Figure 4 Forest area to total biomass potential

Source: own elaboration based on Forest Statistical Yearbook (2024)

Further research applied the analytical tool ArcGIS Pro with the Network Analyst add-on to determine the distance between key wood biomass processing points within the reversed wood biomass supply chain. The distance is calculated according to the current road network in Poland. The values obtained reflect the actual conditions of transport execution by vehicles with a maximum permissible weight (GVW) of 40 tonnes. **Table 9** below shows the distance between biomass processing centres and the geographical centres of voivodeships. Thus, a distance matrix exploit in further research was obtained. This allowed for further calculation of costs and the carbon footprint of wood biomass residues transport processes, depending on the selected location scenario.

Table 9 Distances between the wood processing centre and the geographical centre of the voivodeships

Wood biomass sourcing location (Geographical centre of voivodeship)	Wood biomass processing centre by voivodeship [kilometres]			
	Runowo, 62-035	Biała Rawska, 96-230	Kwidzyna 82-500	Czekanka 42-470
Dolnośląskie	153	289	399	222
Kujawsko-Pomorskie	134	268	110	380
Lubelskie	472	178	515	438
Lubuskie	170	392	411	320
Łódzkie	214	82	275	167
Małopolskie	479	237	484	84
Mazowieckie	322	69	346	262
Opolskie	243	237	466	134
Podkarpackie	642	244	551	264
Podlaskie	515	264	375	450
Pomorskie	304	387	101	483
Śląskie	352	230	445	35
Świętokrzyskie	375	134	399	128
Warmińsko-Mazurskie	337	255	132	450
Wielkopolskie	27	282	267	360
Zachodniopomorskie	288	555	350	550
Minimal distance	27	69	101	35
Average distance	314	256	352	295

Source: own elaboration based on ArcGIS Pro distance calculations

The cost parameter is an important factor in evaluating the efficiency of logistics not only within reverse supply chains. Hence an average value of palletized loading unit of wood biomass was used. In this study, the average cost of a palletized unit load of wood biomass was calculated according to Raúl et al. (2022) research. The pallet unit was assumed to have dimensions of 1.2 m × 0.8 m × 1.5 m (length, width, height). **Table 10** shows the average value of a one loading unit. Within proposed simulation scenarios value of a one loading unit doesn't change with its quantity increase, hence it's value is always multiply of €21.60

Table 10 Wood biomass residues average value

Number of pallets	Value [PLN]
1	€ 21.60
2	€ 43.20
3	€ 64.80

Source: own elaboration based Raúl et al. (2022)

In the next step, the actual price list structure provided by the carrier was used. The proposed price list structure indicates the method of calculating transport freight, considering the distance and number of pallets. For shipments of 1 to 24 pallets, transport is carried out using the LTL mode of transport, while for shipments of more than 24 pallets, dedicated vehicles are used for loadings. It has to consider that the vehicle maximum capacity is 33 pallets. **Table 11** below presents the price list structure, including values for the transport of palletised wood biomass.

Table 11 Anonymized road carrier pricelist for LTL and FTL shipments

Pallets	Distance						Mode of transport
	50 km	51-150 km	151-250 km	251-350 km	351-450 km	451-600 km	
	50	150	250	350	450	600	
1	57.38	85.41	119.32	125.12	139.97	151.88	LTL
2	104.32	161.7	220.38	229.16	256.36	278.18	
3	148.65	230.82	312.96	327.96	366.87	398.07	
4	187.76	297.32	404.24	421.44	471.48	511.6	
5	221.7	345.55	482.5	507.05	567.25	615.5	
6	258.18	395.1	579	592.68	663	719.4	
7	273.84	432.95	621.6	641.06	717.15	778.19	
8	290.64	463.84	674.24	692.56	774.8	840.72	
9	323.64	516.6	750.87	771.39	862.92	936.36	
10	356	568.3	826	848.5	949.2	1030	
11	387.75	618.86	899.47	924	1033.67	1121.67	
12	418.68	668.28	971.52	997.92	1116.36	1211.4	
13	449.15	716.82	1041.95	1070.29	1197.3	1299.22	
14	478.8	764.26	1110.9	1141.14	1276.52	1385.16	
15	507.9	810.6	1178.25	1210.35	1354.05	1469.25	
16	536.32	856	1244.32	1278.24	1429.92	1551.52	
17	564.06	900.49	1308.83	1344.53	1503.99	1632	
18	603.36	962.82	1413.54	1452.06	1624.32	1788.66	
19	643.15	1026.57	1521.9	1540.52	1748.95	1954.15	
20	683.8	1091.4	1634	1622.4	1877.8	2129.2	
21	725.13	1157.52	1749.93	1737.75	2011.17	2314.2	
22	767.36	1224.74	1870	1856.8	2148.96	2509.54	
23	810.29	1293.06	1994.1	1980.07	2291.49	2716.07	
24	853.92	1362.96	2122.56	2107.44	2439.12	2933.76	
25	898.25	1433.75	2255	2239.25	2591.5	3163.75	FTL
26	898.25	1433.75	2255	2239.25	2591.5	3163.75	
27	898.25	1433.75	2255	2239.25	2591.5	3163.75	
28	898.25	1433.75	2255	2239.25	2591.5	3163.75	
29	898.25	1433.75	2255	2239.25	2591.5	3163.75	
30	898.25	1433.75	2255	2239.25	2591.5	3163.75	
31	898.25	1433.75	2255	2239.25	2591.5	3163.75	
32	898.25	1433.75	2255	2239.25	2591.5	3163.75	
33	898.25	1433.75	2255	2239.25	2591.5	3163.75	

Source: own elaboration based on carrier offer

The scenario efficiency evaluation required to determine the parameters of the vehicles intended to handle the wood biomass flows. For this purpose, it was decided to convert the total volume with reference to 40 tonne heavy vehicles. The following

Table 12 outlines their essential parameters for determining the transport work and emissions. For the purpose of evaluating CF emissions, the emission factors presented by the UK Department for Environmental food & rural affairs (UK DEFRA, 2024) were used to calculate this important environmental performance index.

Table 12 Parameters of the vehicle type incorporated in the simulation

Truck type	40 tonnes lorry
Max. payload [kg]	25 000
Max. volume [m3]	91
kgCO2/km	0.633

Source: own elaboration based on UK DEFRA (2024)

The simulation conducted considered individual months of the year and voivodeships. The cost level, distance travelled and total carbon footprint were determined for each location, under each scenario. The following **Table 13** shows the generalized results, subject to further conclusion.

Table 13 Generalised results of cost and CF emission evaluation per location

Voivodeship	Cost Runowo, 62-035	Cost Biała Rawska, 96-230	Cost Kwidziń 82-500	Cost Czekanka 42-470	CF Runowo, 62-035	CF Biała Rawska, 96-230	CF Kwidziń 82-500	CF Czekanka 42-470
Dolnośląskie	63 279 912 zł	62 219 070 zł	72 006 573 zł	62 656 694 zł	2 493 595	4 065 720	5 613 226	3 123 148
Kujawsko-Pomorskie	25 928 239 zł	40 495 072 zł	25 928 239 zł	46 865 236 zł	1 885 143	3 770 287	1 547 506	5 345 929
Lubelskie	79 774 714 zł	56 860 365 zł	79 774 714 zł	65 345 293 zł	6 640 207	2 504 146	7 245 141	6 161 887
Lubuskie	68 182 212 zł	78 356 631 zł	78 356 631 zł	67 705 995 zł	2 391 600	5 514 748	5 782 044	4 501 835
Łódzkie	37 036 799 zł	23 548 342 zł	36 778 116 zł	37 036 799 zł	3 010 602	1 153 595	3 868 764	2 349 395
Małopolskie	65 046 005 zł	46 362 304 zł	65 046 005 zł	29 477 585 zł	6 738 684	3 334 172	6 809 025	1 181 732
Mazowieckie	93 291 132 zł	59 732 571 zł	93 291 132 zł	93 291 132 zł	4 529 971	970 708	4 867 609	3 685 877
Opolskie	25 445 683 zł	25 445 683 zł	35 700 124 zł	16 178 602 zł	3 418 581	3 334 172	6 555 797	1 885 143
Podkarpackie	93 970 367 zł	66 978 483 zł	93 970 367 zł	66 510 673 zł	9 031 806	3 432 649	7 751 597	3 714 014
Podlaskie	86 638 226 zł	61 321 106 zł	70 967 353 zł	70 967 353 zł	7 245 141	3 714 014	5 275 588	6 330 705
Pomorskie	65 458 297 zł	75 755 355 zł	41 911 727 zł	92 483 505 zł	4 276 743	5 444 407	1 420 892	6 794 957
Śląskie	41 661 048 zł	36 251 462 zł	41 661 048 zł	35 998 264 zł	4 952 019	3 235 694	6 260 364	492 388
Świętokrzyskie	44 050 354 zł	24 370 903 zł	44 050 354 zł	24 370 903 zł	5 275 588	1 885 143	5 613 226	1 800 734
Warmińsko-Mazurskie	83 593 087 zł	83 593 087 zł	53 523 094 zł	96 742 876 zł	4 740 995	3 587 400	1 857 007	6 330 705
Wielkopolskie	30 906 918 zł	77 047 944 zł	77 047 944 zł	89 168 136 zł	379 842	3 967 242	3 756 219	5 064 564
Zachodniopomorskie	79 764 610 zł	112 696 342 zł	79 764 610 zł	112 696 342 zł	4 051 652	7 807 870	4 923 882	7 737 529
Total	984 027 602 zł	931 034 720 zł	989 778 030 zł	1 007 495 388 zł	71 062 169	57 721 966	79 147 887	66 500 544

Source: own elaboration.

The results obtained are presented on a cost-emission comparison at **Figure 5**. Thus, it is possible to further verify which wood biomass processing location shows the greatest cost-effectiveness while simultaneously keeping emissions low.

Figure 5 Comparison of emission levels and costs for each location

Source: own elaboration

The analysis conducted also examined the pricing structure applied in the transport of wood biomass. Therefore not only environmental parameters could be taken into consideration while choosing the most efficient location within RSCWB. It has provided the basis for developing a practical approach to assessing the efficiency of wood biomass flows within reverse supply chains.

4.1 Results

The literature review confirmed the relevance of practical aspects in organising logistics within reverse wood biomass supply chains. The research further highlighted the dominant role of the Mazowsze, Warmia-Mazury, Wielkopolska, and West Pomerania voivodeships in terms of potential raw material availability. At the same time, a relatively stable index of wood biomass harvesting was observed across most voivodeships. This parameter corresponds with the deforestation indicator and may suggest the presence of a coordinated and uniform forest management policy at the national level. An examination of transport operators' price lists revealed a strong tendency toward less-than-truckload (LTL) transport for wood biomass. Only in cases where more than 24 pallets are available for shipment does full-truckload (FTL) transport become economically justified. The simulation conducted for four separate locations demonstrated substantial variation in both costs and emissions.

The results indicate that Biała Rawska emerges as the most cost-effective location, despite expectations that sites with greater proximity to major forested areas or industrial hubs might perform better. This outcome can be explained by the specific configuration of Poland's road network and the relative centrality of Biała Rawska, which reduces average transport distances across multiple voivodeships. The central location enables a more balanced distribution of transport work, limiting both costs and emissions when compared to sites that, although closer to large biomass sources, generate disproportionately longer hauls for other regions. The findings highlight the importance of network accessibility and geographical balance, rather than sheer

resource availability, in shaping the efficiency of reversed wood biomass supply chains.

The results for the Czekanka location (post code 42-470) show the highest costs, amounting to 1,007,495,388 PLN, with related emissions of 66,500,544 kgCO₂e. This outcome is based on a simulation in which all biomass processing is redirected to a single site. While the scenario highlights low cost-effectiveness and limited relative efficiency, the potential for reducing the carbon footprint is not justified because of the very high costs. A more favourable option is the location in Biała Rawska (post code 96-230). Here, the total cost is 931,034,720 PLN, the lowest among all assessed locations. Simultaneously CO₂ emissions remain at a comparable level to Czekanka, reaching 57,721,966 kgCO₂e.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Answering to the RQ1 it has been revealed that reverse logistics simulation enables a systematic evaluation of alternative supply chain configurations by quantifying both transport costs and carbon emissions for different processing locations. It makes trade-offs explicit by showing how variations in distance, load size, and network accessibility affect the balance between economic efficiency and environmental performance.

Regarding RQ2 it has been outlined that the key trade-offs between transport costs and carbon emissions emerge from geographical centrality versus proximity to resources. Locations such as Biała Rawska demonstrate that a more central position can minimise average transport distances and thus reduce both costs and emissions, whereas sites closer to major biomass sources may lower emissions locally but generate higher overall costs due to longer hauls elsewhere.

Despite of this research contributions, this research is subject to identified limitations. The simulations were conducted at a national level, which may overlook local variations in biomass supply and logistics practices. The analysis focused mainly on cost and carbon emissions, leaving out factors such as biomass quality, seasonality, and storage requirements. Furthermore, the use of static price lists and transport conditions does not capture actual market fluctuations. Finally, as the research is based on the Polish context, its findings may have limited generalisability to other regions.

Future studies could explore the application of multi-criteria analysis, allowing for the inclusion of a broader set of qualitative parameters in the evaluation. Factors such as the moisture content and contamination level of wood biomass are crucial for its subsequent processing, and therefore parameters enabling automated identification at individual processing facilities may provide significant added value. The current research adopts a general perspective, focusing mainly on determining the most suitable location based on cost and transport emission criteria.

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